

SIMULATION OF THE INTERMEDIATE VELOCITY IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF WOVEN COMPOSITE LAMINATES APPLYING PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE MODELS FOR PLYS AND INTERFACES

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ABSTRACT

A strategy for modelling impact on woven fabric reinforced laminates at intermediate velocities using the framework of the explicit finite element method is presented such that the energy absorption of the laminate can be predicted and assigned to individual failure mechanisms. Thereby a “stacked shell” approach is utilized where each ply of the laminate is discretized by an individual layer of shell elements. The damage and failure behaviour of the plies is modelled using an energy based continuum damage mechanics approach. Tensile and compressive ply damage along the fibre directions, as well as shear damage are considered. Additionally plastic deformations due to shear loads are captured. Delamination is accounted for by modelling the interfaces between individual plies using cohesive zone elements in combination with a traction-separation based constitutive law. Element deletion is utilized to cope with fully damaged elements and, furthermore, contact definitions between delaminated plies are included. Hence, the approach is capable of predicting the impact response of laminated composites up to complete perforation. In order to show the predictive capabilities of the presented modelling approach, a rectangular carbon fabric/epoxy reinforced laminated plate with quasi-isotropic layup in a drop tower test setup is modelled. The predicted energy absorption of the plate, as well as the deformation behaviour and the damage and failure behaviour are compared to equivalent experimental results. Additionally, the contributions of individual failure mechanisms to the total energy absorption are predicted. The described modelling strategy is particularly advantageous in terms computational efficiency, while maintaining detailed and quantitative predictions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Laminated composites are increasingly used in aerospace and other applications, where their high specific stiffness and strength lead to a favourable application in lightweight components and structures. Moreover, they exhibit good environmental and fatigue resistance and are easy to form during manufacturing. However, fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites show a complex damage and failure behaviour involving delamination, matrix cracking, fibre rupture and plasticity-like effects. All of them may occur during out-of-plane impact where the particular extent of individual failure mechanisms is depending on the structural impact response.

Experimental testing of the impact behaviour of FRPs may be used to evaluate the effects of predefined loading conditions on certain specimen configurations. However, it is very time consuming and expensive to investigate several different impact scenarios. The experimental investigation of the impact behaviour of structural “real life” components involves even more difficulties. In this regard, numerical simulations by means of advanced methods within the framework of the Finite Element Method (FEM) provide a powerful tool for predicting the damage and failure behaviour of laminated composites subjected to impact. Many publications focus on low velocity impact and the prediction of the impact resistance and the general behaviour, cf. [1-5]. On the other hand, also high velocity (and ballistic) impact has been studied within the literature, cf. [6-9], where mainly the prediction of the ballistic limit is intended. However, to the authors’ knowledge, very little published literature is

dealing with intermediate velocity – intermediate mass impacts. Furthermore, the prediction of the energy absorption of individual failure mechanisms of laminated composite structures under impact loads hasn't been addressed within the literature yet.

This paper aims at providing a modelling strategy for simulating the impact behaviour of fabric reinforced laminates with a special focus on the prediction of the energy absorption of individual failure mechanisms, i.e. ply fracture, plasticity-like effects and delamination. Thereby, a “stacked shell” approach is utilized where each ply of the laminate is discretized by an individual layer of shell elements. The constitutive behaviour of the plies is described using an energy based continuum damage mechanics (CDM) approach. Adjacent layers are connected via cohesive zone elements which are assigned a traction separation based constitutive law in order to account for delamination. Element deletion is utilized to cope with fully damaged elements and, furthermore, contact definitions between delaminated plies are included. Accordingly, the approach is capable of predicting the impact response of laminated composites up to complete perforation. The presented modelling approach is applied using the explicit finite element code Abaqus/Explicit v6.14 (Dassault Systemes Simulia Corp., Providence, RI, USA). As an example, numerical predictions of a rectangular laminated composite plate with quasi-isotropic layup in a drop-tower test setup are presented and compared to results of equivalent experiments. It shall be noted that particular advantages in terms of computational efficiency are achieved due to the shell modelling approach, while maintaining detailed and quantitative predictions.

2 MODELLING OF WOVEN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Woven composite laminates exhibit a complex microstructure and undergo different modes of failure occurring at various length scales. The smallest length scale within the context of the present work is represented by individual fibres, an intermediate (meso) scale may be defined by the thickness of a single weave whereas the macroscopic scale is described by the dimensions of some component. The failure modes may be categorised by their location of occurrence into intra-laminar and inter-laminar mechanisms. The intra-laminar failure mechanisms include matrix cracking, fibre rupture and plasticity-like effects whereas inter-laminar failure denotes the debonding of adjacent plies, i.e. delamination. In order to capture these failure mechanisms within FEM simulations, a suitable length scale for the geometrical modelling of such laminates in combination with appropriate constitutive laws have to be chosen.

Within this work, a woven composite laminate is modelled at the meso-scale, where the laminate is considered as a stack of homogeneous orthotropic layers connected via inter-laminar interfaces, cf. [10]. Thereby, each ply is discretised by an individual layer of shell elements whereas the interfaces are represented by hexahedral elements in combination with a cohesive zone approach. These cohesive zone elements (CZE) share the nodes of the adjacent shell layers located at the corresponding reference planes. This composition is called stacked shell approach (SSA) in the following and is schematically depicted in Fig. 1, where the reference planes of the shell layers are shown in green colour with the corresponding nodes as green dots. The CZEs between these shell layers are illustrated by the shaded areas where the black lines connecting the nodes of the shell reference planes indicate CZE edges. A major benefit of the proposed SSA is represented by the use of shell elements for modelling the intra-ply behaviour of the composite. This way, the computational efficiency is

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the stacked shell approach (SSA). The reference planes of the shell layers are shown in green colour where the corresponding nodes are marked as green dots. The CZEs are illustrated as shaded areas confined by black lines.

increased while maintaining an accurate representation of the kinematic behaviour of the plies. Furthermore, if explicit FEM formulations are applied, the stable time increment will not be negatively influenced by the small thickness of the plies, as it will be the case when solid elements are used.

In the following, the constitutive models applied for modelling the above mentioned intra-ply and inter-ply failure mechanisms are summarized. The mechanisms associated with intra-ply failure are intended to be described within the ply constitutive behaviour of the shell layers, while delamination shall be predicted by the constitutive behaviour of the CZEs.

2.1 Ply constitutive behaviour

The fabric reinforced plies are modelled as homogeneous orthotropic material in combination with an energy based CDM approach to account for tensile and compressive fibre damage. Furthermore, plastic deformation and damage under shear loading are modelled in order to capture the matrix dominated shear response of the ply. The described constitutive model is readily available within the FEM package Abaqus/Explicit as a built-in VUMAT user subroutine and can be accessed by assigning a predefined material name in the input file, cf. [11]. In the following, a summary of the material model and the governing equations, based on [11], is given.

The woven fabric reinforcement considered within the present material model is assumed to have orthogonal fibre (tow) directions. Considering the elasto-damage response, the stress-strain relations read

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{12}^{el} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{(1-d_1)E_1} & \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_1} & 0 \\ & \frac{1}{(1-d_2)E_2} & 0 \\ \text{symm.} & & \frac{1}{(1-d_{12})2G_{12}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix} . \quad (1)$$

Plane stress conditions are assumed, where the 1 and 2 directions represent the fibre directions. The strain components are denoted as ε_{ij} whereas stress components are identified by σ_{ij} . E_1 and E_2 are the Young's moduli along the fibre directions, ν_{12} is the Poisson's ratio and G_{12} is the shear modulus. The damage variables along the fibre directions, d_1 and d_2 , are further distinguished in tensile and compressive fibre failure modes as d_{1+} , d_{1-} , d_{2+} and d_{2-} where tensile or compressive states are evaluated according to the stress state in the corresponding direction. The damage variable d_{12} is related to matrix micro-cracking due to shear deformation.

Considering the response along the fibre directions, the initiation and evolution of the individual damage mechanisms are described using effective stresses defined as,

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{1+} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle}{(1-d_{1+})} \quad \tilde{\sigma}_{1-} = \frac{\langle -\sigma_{11} \rangle}{(1-d_{1-})} , \quad (2)$$

for the 1 direction, where similar expressions are used to define the effective stresses for the 2 direction. The angle brackets $\langle \rangle$ in Eq. (2) represent the Macaulay operator. In the following, the fibre failure modes are represented by the index α , which may be substituted by 1+, 1-, 2+ or 2-. The elastic domain is defined in terms of damage activation functions as

$$F_\alpha = \phi_\alpha - r_\alpha \leq 0 \quad . \quad (3)$$

The functions ϕ_α denote the loading functions and r_α the damage thresholds which read as follows,

$$\phi_\alpha = \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_\alpha}{X_\alpha} \quad \text{and} \quad r_\alpha(t) = \max_{\tau \leq t} \phi_\alpha(\tau) \quad , \quad (4)$$

where the variables X_α denote the tensile and compressive strengths along the fibre directions. The damage thresholds are initially set to one and increase according to the consistency condition $\dot{\phi}_\alpha = \dot{r}_\alpha$ upon damage activation. Furthermore, the Kuhn-Tucker conditions are assumed to hold for the damage activation functions and thresholds. Hence, the loading functions in combination with the damage thresholds describe the size of the elastic domain at a given time, t , within the loading history. Damage due to one of the failure modes, α , is assumed to propagate when the value of the corresponding loading function exceeds the one of the corresponding damage threshold. Damage propagation is modelled as exponential strain softening, where the evolution of the damage variables, d_α , is described using the relations,

$$d_\alpha = 1 - \frac{1}{r_\alpha} \exp[-A_\alpha(r_\alpha - 1)] \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{d}_\alpha \geq 0 \quad . \quad (5)$$

The coefficients A_α are defined as,

$$A_\alpha = \frac{2g_0^\alpha L_c}{G_{lc}^\alpha - g_0^\alpha L_c} \quad \text{with} \quad g_0^\alpha = \frac{X_\alpha^2}{2E_\alpha} \quad , \quad (6)$$

and relate the damage evolution, Eq. (5), to corresponding critical energy release rates, $G_{lc}^\alpha \cdot L_c$ represents a characteristic element length. Hence, mesh adjusted softening is implemented, cf. [12], ensuring that the correct amount of energy is dissipated as long as L_c is small enough so that the denominator of A_α stays positive, cf. Eq. (6).

Considering the response under shear loading, damage initiation is modelled in a similar manner as for the response along the fibre directions, cf. Eqs. (2)-(4). The evolution of the shear damage variable, d_{12} , is defined as,

$$d_{12} = \min[\beta_{12} \ln(r_{12}), d_{12}^{\max}] \quad , \quad (7)$$

where β_{12} and d_{12}^{\max} are material properties to be experimentally determined. Hence, it is assumed that shear damage increases proportional to the logarithm of the damage threshold until a specified maximum value is reached. Additionally, plastic behaviour under shear loading is incorporated. Therefore, the shear strain is decomposed into an elastic and a plastic part,

$$\varepsilon_{12} = \varepsilon_{12}^{el} + \varepsilon_{12}^{pl} \quad , \quad (8)$$

and the yield function,

$$F = |\tilde{\sigma}_{12}| - \tilde{\sigma}_0(\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}) \leq 0 \quad , \quad (9)$$

is introduced, where $\tilde{\sigma}_{12}$ identifies the effective shear stress, cf. Eq. (2), and $\tilde{\sigma}_0$ represents the hardening function which reads,

$$\tilde{\sigma}_0(\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}) = \tilde{\sigma}_{y0} + (\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl})^p C \quad . \quad (10)$$

As can be seen, isotropic hardening is modelled where $\tilde{\sigma}_{y0}$ is the initial effective yield stress, $\bar{\varepsilon}^{pl}$ the equivalent plastic strain and p and C are constants for the calibration of the hardening curve. Associated flow is assumed and the flow rule reads as,

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{12}^{pl} = \dot{\varepsilon}^{pl} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_{12}} = \dot{\varepsilon}^{pl} \text{sign}(\tilde{\sigma}_{12}) \quad . \quad (11)$$

2.2 Interface constitutive behaviour

The interface constitutive response is modelled using the Abaqus built-in traction-separation based constitutive model for CZEs, cf. [13]. Within the elastic range the normal and shear traction components are assumed to be uncoupled. Damage initiation is predicted according to a quadratic nominal stress criterion. Damage evolution is modelled using a scalar damage variable, where delamination is predicted when the corresponding critical energy release rate of the interface is met. Mixed-mode conditions are accounted for using a criterion proposed by Benzeggagh and Kenane, cf. [14], which evaluates the critical energy release rate for a given mode-mix based on the pure mode quantities. A linear softening relation based on an effective displacement is assumed. For further details on the constitutive model and the corresponding equations, the reader is referred to section 32.5.6 of the Abaqus Analysis User's Guide [13].

3 APPLICATION EXAMPLE: DROP TOWER TEST – FEM MODEL

The described modelling approach is exemplified by simulating the response of a laminated composite plate in a drop tower experiment. The laminate consists of eight carbon fabric reinforced epoxy plies with a thickness of $h_{ply} = 0.4216\text{mm}$ each and the outer dimensions of the plate are 150x100mm. A quasi-isotropic layup defined as $[0/45/0/45]_s$ is applied, where the 0 degree direction is parallel to the longer edge of the plate. The bottom side of the plate is supported by a steel frame with an inner cut-out of 125x75mm and the top side is pressed down via four rubber pads of 12.2mm diameter at the corners of a 100x87.5mm rectangle. The laminate is subjected to a transverse, central impact by a spherical steel impactor of 20mm diameter. A schematic illustration of the setup is shown in Fig. 2.

3.1 Geometrical modelling and boundary conditions

The laminate is modelled by applying the SSA described in the previous section. The mid-plane of each ply of the laminate is discretised by a regular mesh of linearly interpolated 4-noded shell elements with an edge length of 0.5mm. Five integration points (section points) are assigned through

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the simulated drop tower test setup.

the thickness of each shell layer, where the thickness integration is conducted using the Simpson rule. The interfaces between adjacent plies are discretized by 8-noded, brick shaped, CZEs where the nodes of the reference planes of the shell layers are shared with the CZEs. Hence, the CZEs have the same in-plane dimensions as the shell elements of the plies and their geometrical height corresponds to the distance between the reference planes of adjacent shell layers, i.e. the ply thickness. However, the constitutive thickness of the CZEs used within the formulation of the interface constitutive law is assumed to be 1mm, cf. [13].

The rubber pads as well as the frame are considered to be rigid and, accordingly, modelled using 4-noded rigid elements with average edge lengths of 0.5mm, where their reference nodes are fixed in all degrees of freedom. Contact is defined between the top surface of the laminate and the rubber pads, as well as between the top surface of the frame and the bottom surface of the laminate.

The impactor is also considered to be rigid and is discretized using 4-noded and 8-noded solid elements with an average edge length of 0.5mm at the outer surface. The movement of the corresponding reference node is fixed for every degree of freedom except the translational movement along the z-direction, cf. Fig. 2. An initial velocity of $v_z = 20\text{m/s}$ is assigned to the impactor and its total mass is set to 2kg. This yields an impact energy of 400J. The mass results from the sled of the drop tower test system and additionally added ballast. For the sake of simplicity, the total amount of mass within the moving part of the drop tower is assigned to the impactor. Contact is defined between the impactor and the top surfaces of each ply.

3.2 Material properties

The above described model is simulated with the explicit FEM code Abaqus/Explicit. One aspect of this explicit solver is, that every element within the computational domain has to be assigned some mass density. The mass density as well as the element geometry influence the stable time increment of the explicit time integration. Hence, small mass densities in combination with small element dimensions, as occurring within the interfaces of the laminate, lead to very small time increments. In order to compensate this disadvantage, a constitutive thickness of 1mm is used in the constitutive model of the CZEs and the total mass of the laminate is distributed between the plies and the interfaces. In order to retain the dynamic behaviour of the laminate it has to be ensured that the nodal masses remain unchanged in the model. The assigned mass densities are listed in Tab. 1. The nominal laminate mass density ρ_{lam} is split into a mass density assigned to the top and bottom plies, $\rho_{\text{ply}}^{\text{out}}$, a mass density assigned to the inner plies, $\rho_{\text{ply}}^{\text{in}}$, and a mass density per unit area assigned to the interface, ρ_{int} .

The material properties necessary to define the constitutive behaviour of the plies, cf. section 2.1, are given in the following. Table 2 states the elastic constants of a single ply, whereas the properties describing the damage and failure behaviour along the fibre directions of a ply are listed in Tab. 3. The elastic constants, as well as the nominal strengths are taken from corresponding material data sheets. The critical energy release rates are estimated from values determined for unidirectional (UD) reinforced carbon/epoxy laminates in [15] by taking half of the value determined for UD laminates. The parameters defining the plastic, as well as the damage behaviour of a ply under shear loads are given in Tab.4. These parameters have been evaluated from available test data of UD reinforced carbon/epoxy laminates collected at the Polymer Competence Center Leoben (Leoben, Austria). The material parameters defining the constitutive response of the interface are listed in Tab. 5. The elastic properties are chosen so that a quasi-rigid connection between the plies is ensured within the elastic regime.

ρ_{lam}	$\rho_{\text{ply}}^{\text{in}}$	$\rho_{\text{ply}}^{\text{out}}$	ρ_{int}
1560 kg/m ³	520 kg/m ³	1040 kg/m ³	0.438464kg/m ²

Table 1: Mass densities assigned to the plies and interfaces. See the text for an explanation.

elastic constants	E_1 56.813 GPa	E_2 56.813 GPa	ν_{12} 0.047	G_{12} 4.2058 GPa
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Table 2: Material properties describing the elastic behaviour of the carbon fabric/epoxy ply. The 1 and 2 directions are parallel to the fibre directions.

nominal strengths	X_{1+} 802.11 MPa	X_{1-} 707.88 MPa	X_{2+} 802.11 MPa	X_{2-} 707.88 MPa
crit. energy release rates	G_{lc}^{1+} 44.9 N/mm	G_{lc}^{1-} 39.15 N/mm	G_{lc}^{2+} 44.9 N/mm	G_{lc}^{2-} 39.15 N/mm

Table 3: Material properties describing the damage and failure behaviour along the fibre directions of the carbon fabric/epoxy ply. The 1 and 2 directions are parallel to the fibre directions.

S_{12}	β_{12}	d_{12}^{\max}	$\tilde{\sigma}_{y0}$	C	p
115.83 MPa	0.18634	1.0	55.0 MPa	669.94 MPa	0.823

Table 4: Shear damage and plasticity parameters of the carbon fabric/epoxy ply. S_{12} denotes the shear strength.

elastic properties	E_{33} 10 ⁶ MPa	E_{31} 10 ⁶ MPa	E_{32} 10 ⁶ MPa
nominal strengths	t_3^o 60 MPa	t_1^o 79.289 MPa	t_2^o 79.289 MPa
crit. energy release rates	G_{lc} 0.9 N/mm	G_{llc} 2.0 N/mm	G_{lllc} 2.0 N/mm

Table 5: Interface properties describing the initial elastic response of the interface, as well as damage initiation and propagation. The 3 direction identifies the direction perpendicular to the laminate.

The nominal strength for pure mode I loading of the interface, t_3^o , is estimated whereas the strengths for the mode II and mode III fracture, t_1^o and t_2^o , are taken from a corresponding material data sheet. The critical energy release rates are estimated from values published in [16].

3.3 Simulation specific settings

As discussed above, the stiffnesses of ply and interface elements are degraded according to the evolution of individual damage variables whereby zero stiffness is retained for fully damaged elements. Hence, fully damaged elements may be excessively distorted leading to small stable time increments during the numerical integration or even to the termination of the computation. In order to overcome these problems, damaged elements are deleted during the analysis according to the following criteria. Considering the shell layers discretising the plies, a shell element is deleted when

one of the damage variables describing damage along the fibre directions, d_{1+} , d_{1-} , d_{2+} or d_{2-} , reaches a value of 0.99 at one integration point but all associated section points. A CZE is deleted when the corresponding damage variable reaches a value of 1.0 at all integration points. Furthermore, the option “cohesive compression damage” is used in order to allow for the deletion of CZEs which are fully damaged due to shear but are under normal compression.

All contact constraints within the simulation are enforced using the general contact algorithm of Abaqus/Explicit, for which a penalty algorithm is utilized to compute contact forces. Since damaged CZEs are deleted according to the criterion mentioned above, they are no longer available to maintain the contact behaviour between the plies. In order to retain realistic behaviour after delamination has occurred, contact is defined between adjacent plies where the ply thickness used for the contact calculation is scaled by a factor of 0.9 compared to the geometrical thickness. Thereby, it shall be ensured that this additionally defined contact is just active when the corresponding CZEs have been deleted. Furthermore, the plies are excluded from self-contact for numerical reasons. The penalty stiffness used for the contact enforcement between adjacent plies is scaled by a factor of 0.1 compared the value automatically determined by the contact algorithm. This scaling is chosen so that the work done by the penalty forces is small compared to other energy contributions. For the penalty stiffness of the contact between the impactor and the laminate the value automatically determined by the contact algorithm is used. It shall be noted, that frictionless behaviour is assumed for every contact definition.

Preceding simulations have shown that anisotropic damage in combination with reduced integrated elements induces hourglassing. Although hourglass controls are available within Abaqus/Explicit, a non-negligible amount of energy is attributed to the artificially introduced stiffnesses associated with these controls. Therefore, fully integrated elements are applied within the present simulations.

Abaqus/Explicit introduces, by default, a so-called bulk viscosity associated with the damping of volumetric straining. The default values have been applied for the shell layers, whereas the bulk viscosity parameters for the CZEs have been set to zero, as recommended in the user’s guide, cf. [13].

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following, the predictions obtained using the described model are presented and compared to results from equivalent experiments carried out at the Polymer Competence Center Leoben (Leoben, Austria) with specimens manufactured at FACC AG (Ried im Innkreis, Austria). Figure 3 shows a comparison of the predicted and experimentally obtained failure pattern at the back face of the laminated plate after the 400J impact. The depicted cracks in Fig. 3 (left) arise due to propagating damage in the individual plies. As can be seen, total perforation occurred and the predicted and experimental failure pattern agree very well.

Figure 3: Failure pattern at the back face of the laminated plate after 400J impact. Predicted impact response (left). Experimentally observed response (right). The images are depicted at an equal length scale.

Figure 4: Comparison of the total energy absorption of the laminated plate (left) and the total force on the impactor (right) with respect to time. The black lines indicate the predicted response whereas grey lines represent experimentally measured values. At the time $t = 0$ ms first contact between the impactor and the plate is observed.

Hence, the qualitative behaviour of the laminate including the spatial distribution of damage is well captured. Besides the prediction of the general impact behaviour, the energy absorption of the laminate is assessed quantitatively using the presented modelling approach. The left plot in Fig. 4 shows a comparison of the total energy absorbed by the plate with respect to time. The black solid line indicates the predicted energy absorption and the grey solid lines represent the experimentally measured energy absorptions. The predicted energy absorption has been evaluated as the reduction of the kinetic energy of the impactor during the impact event, whereas the measured energy absorption has been determined with respect to the recorded force-time response of the impactor. Therefore, also the total force acting on the impactor surface is compared with respect to time, cf. Fig. 4 right. The predicted and measured energy absorption, as well as the force responses show very good agreement throughout the whole duration of the impact event. Furthermore, the time of occurrence and magnitude of the peak force are identical in the simulation and the experiment, cf. Fig. 4 (right). Starting at 0.6ms after contact between the impactor and the plate is established, it can be seen that the predicted force on the impactor is slightly higher than the measured one. However, the slopes of the two curves are almost identical. This circumstance finally leads to the slight over-prediction of the absorbed energy, cf. Fig. 4.

The left side of Fig. 5 illustrates an overlay of the predicted delamination areas of all seven interfaces of the laminate after the 400J impact. The darkness of the shadings indicates whether delamination occurs at every interface or just individual ones. The black square illustrates the projected delaminated area measured via a C-scan of the impacted plate. Again, very good correspondence is found. Furthermore, it has been found in the experiments that the interface closest to the back face of the laminate shows the largest delaminated area. This behaviour is also predicted by the simulation. On the right side of Fig. 5 the energy absorbed by the individual mechanisms being active during the impact event is shown, as predicted by the present model. The bar identified by the index “elastic” represents the elastic part of the strain energy stored within the plate and the bar with index “kinetic” identifies the kinetic energy of the plate. Hence, the plate is still experiencing some oscillation after it has been perforated by the impactor. The sum of these two mechanisms represents the recoverable part of the absorbed energy. As can be seen, the highest amount of energy is absorbed by ply fracture, cf. the bar with index “damage” in Fig. 5 right. Slightly less energy is consumed by plastic deformation of the plies due to shear (index “plast”). Delamination of plies leads to almost the

Figure 5: Overlay of predicted delamination areas (left). A value of 0.0 means that no delamination is predicted, whereas 1.0 corresponds to delamination at every interface. The coordinates are given in mm where the plate is impacted at the origin. Predicted energy absorption with respect to individual mechanisms (right).

same amount of absorbed energy (index “delam”). Hence, all of the above mentioned mechanisms are of almost equal importance regarding the overall energy absorption of the laminate.

Finally, the computational efficiency of the presented model is discussed. The model contains about 3.1 million degrees of freedom, where the computation of 1 ms of time took about 6 hours using a cluster system with 16 CPUs at 3.3GHz. Having in mind the model’s level of detail (every ply and every interface is modelled), the computation time is very promising. Furthermore, the model has not yet been optimised regarding the element size. Hence, further improvements with respect to computational efficiency are expected.

5 SUMMARY

A strategy for modelling impact on woven fabric reinforced laminates by means of the finite element method is presented. Thereby, a so-called stacked shell approach (SSA) is utilized where each ply of the laminate is discretised by an individual layer of shell elements. The damage and failure behaviour of the plies is modelled using an energy based continuum damage mechanics approach. The interfaces between the individual plies are modelled by cohesive zone elements in combination with a traction-separation based constitutive law. In order to show the capabilities of the presented SSA, a rectangular carbon fabric/epoxy reinforced laminated plate with quasi-isotropic layup in a drop tower test setup is modelled. The simulations are conducted using the explicit finite element code Abaqus/Explicit v6.14. Comparisons with equivalent experimental results show that the deformation pattern as well as the damage and failure behaviour can be well predicted. Further, the predicted and measured amount of energy absorbed by the plate are found to match closely. The simulations reveal that the energies absorbed by ply fracture, plastic deformation of the plies due to shear, delamination and the recoverable part of the absorbed energy are of almost equal importance regarding the overall energy absorption of the laminate. The computational efficiency of the presented SSA is very promising at the current state, although the model is not yet optimised regarding the element size. Hence, further improvements with respect to computation time are expected.

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